

Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employees Attitude toward work In International Non-Governmental Sector

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Abstract

This research aimed to measure effect of performance appraisal on employees' attitude toward work performance. For the objective, the study used data from international Non-Governmental Organizations (I-NGOs) in Kabul. The study used structured questionnaire to analyze the effect of performance appraisal on employee's attitude towards work. Primary data was collected mainly from senior, middle, and lower level management. A sample of 150 respondents were selected based on purposive sampling technique. The effect was analyzed through correlation and regression analysis. The results indicated that 360 degree and peer review appraisal significantly affect the employees' attitude towards work. But the 360 degree appraisal has negative effect, the possible reason may be the negative connotation of punishment attached with 360 degree appraisal. Self-review was found with no effect on attitude towards work. Performance appraisal had an impact on employees' performance, thus, when appraisal is fairly done, employees tend to be motivated and it reflects in their work output. On the other side, when it's poorly done employees become bitter and it affects their performance. Effective and fair performance appraisal process would enhance employees' performance. This study recommends that performance appraisal should be used as a supporting tool for policy making. Employees should be ensured of transparency in appraisal process and it must be made sure that employees' perceive appraisal process as a tool of workforce development.

Keywords: Performance Appraisal, Employees' Work Attitude, 360 Degree Appraisal, Self-Review, Peer Review

JEL Codes: M12, M19, O15

1. Introduction

Numerous organizations were affected by Frederick Taylor's "Logical Management" endeavors of the mid twentieth century. It is along these lines trusted that proceeded with "accomplishment of every organization relies upon its Performance appraisal". Worker performance evaluation is

a standout amongst the most utilized administration devices. Performance appraisal have expansive outcomes on individuals. If evaluators in any capacity oppress workers, these people can endure decimating and conceivably weakening results. Given the likelihood that unfavorable judgments can be made around a person's performance, it is conceivable that Performance appraisal won't not be reasonable. Evaluators may permit their predispositions, biases and cliché mentalities to adversely impact the result.

In the early 20th century, Performance appraisal were utilized as a part of bigger organizations for the most part for regulatory purposes, for example, making advancements and deciding pay rates and rewards. Since the 1960s, in any case, organizations and analysts have progressively focused on the utilization of representative assessments for motivational and authoritative arranging purposes. For sure, for some organizations, Performance appraisal has turned into a vital device for expanding the adequacy of all parts of the organization, from staffing and improvement to creation and client benefit.

In hierarchical setting, Performance appraisal is characterized as an organized formal communication between a subordinate and a predominant, that as a rule appears as an intermittent meeting which could either be yearly or semi-yearly, in which the work performance of the subordinate is inspected and talked about with the view to recognizing quality and shortcomings and open doors for development and ability improvement. Moorhead and Griffin (1992) portray it as a procedure of assessing work practices by estimation and correlation with already settled benchmarks, recording results, and imparting them back to the worker. It is an action between a supervisor and a worker.

Amid Performance appraisal gatherings, various strategies can be utilized to report, or record, or outline performance talks, running from accounts, rating scales, basic episode rundowns, and so on. The fundamental reason for evaluations is to help oversee staff successfully and utilize HR

and eventually, to enhance profitability.

A few investigations feature that some of representative's report being casualties of out of line performance assessments (Blasé and Blase, 2003; Bryne, 1971; Huo and Tyler, 2001). The result, the strategies took after, data utilized, and the relational progression between an evaluator and an evacuee of performance appraisals may effect on worker adversely. For instance, an out of line performance audit may bring about a worker being terminated or expelled from his activity or perhaps get low rate performance appraisals. The passionate worry of losing one's activity because of an unacceptable performance appraisal can bring about physical signs from laziness to muscle torment to heart and respiratory issues (Blasé and Blase, 2003). In another circumstance, a representative may encounter comparative enthusiastic and physical responses if an unreasonable performance appraisal brought about his or her being put on audit which would require more regular performance appraisal until except if to enhance him/her self.

Where performance appraisals are directed appropriately, the two administrators and subordinates have announced the experience as advantageous and positive and may come about positive or negative effect on representative state of mind too. So the overall objective of the study is to analyze the effect of performance appraisal on employees' work attitude. The study uses three dimensions of performance appraisals including 360 degree appraisal, self-review, and peer review appraisal.

1.1 Problem Statement

An ample amount of work has been done in the field of performance appraisal like Wright (2001), Marcky and Johnson (2000), Olson and Maio (2003) and Petty, et al (2003). Less has been done to measure and empirically analyze the effect of performance appraisal on employees' work attitude, especially in developing countries context. Afghanistan is no exception to the statement where organizations do not pay more attention to relating performance appraisal and work attitude. Performance appraisal

process can affect the employees' attitude towards works and that is why this paper analyzes such relationship of performance appraisal and employees' attitude towards work. This paper will be considered as a helping tool for effective decision making both at policy making and implementation level for profit and non-profit organizations.

2. Literature Review

Individuals are vital asset and like all assets they should be overseen legitimately to help them perform at their pinnacle (Wright, 2001). As per Marcky and Johnson (2000) Human Resources Management (HRM) alludes to every one of the procedures and exercises went for using all representatives to accomplish authoritative closures. They recommended that HRM includes; staffing, performance administration, retention, compliance and change administration.

As organizations grow, a formal performance appraisal framework helps regulatory choice, for example, pay increments and advancements, repetition or end, advancement needs and for workers, the procedure may help them in profession decisions and may build their responsibility and fulfilment because of upgrades in organization's correspondence (Weise and Buckley, 1998). To get most of this asset from individuals, they should be roused as individuals can't be persuaded Cole (2001), and Wright (2001). They went further to state that, individuals inspire themselves and administrators can give flora to enable them to be spurred.

The three noteworthy targets of (HRM) are to draw in possibly qualified occupation candidates, hold alluring representatives and propel workers (Kramar, et al 1997). The point being to impact the money related main concern, through enhanced efficiency, enhanced nature of work life and legitimate consistence. One method for accomplishing this is by assessing representatives on their activity performance. This is said to encourage sentiments of prosperity and improve performance (Sargent and Terry, 1998) and give representatives work fulfilment, inspiration and contribution in

the work environment (Parker, 1993).

Various organizations utilize a formal or casual appraisal framework that measures representatives' performance and commitment (Carroll and Scheiner, 1982). Cones and Jenkins (2000) propose that performance evaluation is an ordered procedure in which, for a predefined period, all or a gathering of representatives' work practices or attributes are independently appraised, judged, or portrayed by a ratter and the outcomes are kept by the association. DeNisi et al (1984) showed that performance evaluation is an activity in social observation and discernment installed in a hierarchical setting requiring both formal and casual judgment. Karol (1996) considered performance appraisal to incorporate a correspondence occasion booked between a director and a representative explicitly to evaluate that worker's past activity performance and talking about pertinent territories of future occupation performance.

2.1 The Concept of Performance Appraisal (PA)

A huge bearing of research with respect to PA adequacy and methodologies for assessment has focused on worker fulfilment and impression of the procedure. Along these lines, scientists and specialists have taken a more complete perspective of performance appraisal framework adequacy and assessment of frameworks. One regular subject of late research is that demeaners of the framework's clients toward the procedure decide to an expansive degree a definitive adequacy of performance evaluation framework (Roberts, 1990). Despite the definition or the segments included, PA in many organizations is formal, and organized. The procedure is for the most part characterized to incorporate a meeting between the ratter and the to whom rating is given, and additionally performance documentation required by the formal assessment framework. One descriptor let alone for most definitions is that performance evaluation is regularly fear by members. Folger and Lewis (1993) recommend that Performance appraisal commonly cause an indistinguishable level of energy from paying duties.

Folger et al (1992) contended that as opposed to concentrating on exactness, the objective of PA ought to guarantee decency all the while, which is a more achievable objective. Analysts began to embrace the view point that representatives' impression of reasonableness are more critical than target exactness of the evaluation framework. On the off chance that an exact appraisal framework is seen as uncalled for, it might prompt negative results or, it is conceivable that a precise evaluation device that is seen as reasonable may not prompt negative results. Reasonableness ought to be embraced because precision isn't achievable as well as on the grounds that it is a critical societal esteem and sentiments of unfairness have imperative results for the general public and the working environment (Sabbagh, et al, 1994, Sashkin and Williams, 1990). Reasonableness of HR rehearses merits consideration from a humanistic perspective too (Koys, 1991; Ogilvie, 1986; Bretz and Judge, 1994).

It would appear to be coherent and vital that representatives want to be assessed on work criteria that is exact and identifies with parts of their activity that is inside their control. For instance, Boswell and Boudreau (2000) feature precise performance appraisal can be an essential indicator of representative states of mind towards their director, the activity and the PA procedure. They go further to recommend that if the assessment isn't seen as exact, they may thus effect on the procedure accomplishing its convenience in the organization and notwithstanding contributing adversely in singular conduct and authoritative performance. Pettijohn et al (2001) bolster this and propose that obscure, unclear and improper criteria may bring down inspiration accordingly prompting negative responses towards performance assessment.

Gabris and Ihrke (2000) revealed that authority believability of prompt bosses is altogether connected with whether workers see performance appraisal frameworks as procedurally reasonable and instrumentally just and proper. Their investigation of province government experts investigated this issue and in addition related issues of employment burnout,

work fulfilment, chief advancement and collaboration between authoritative units. Boswell and Boudreau, (2000) found a critical positive connection between worker states of mind and procedurally just Performance appraisal and underscored the significance representatives put on decency.

Performance appraisal at times have the notoriety of making pressure between an administrator and subordinate. Nonetheless, solid and successful performance surveys share regular segments that make them positive experience and augment the advantage of leading and taking an interest in them. Underscoring the great and helping a worker headed for development are essential segments of compelling performance evaluations. A Variety of Components might be incorporated into the performance evaluation process. Landy and Farr (1980) exhibited a model of performance evaluation that included 13 interrelating factors: position attributes, organization qualities, the motivation behind the rating, the rating procedure, scale advancement, the rating instrument, rater and ratee attributes, the perception and capacity of performance information, the judgment of that performance, the appraisal of this data, performance portrayal, and individual response.

2.2 Types of Performance Appraisal

Organizations receive and utilize diverse Performance appraisal relying upon the requirements and nature of the activity, work and the organization. The most ordinarily utilized evaluation methods include 360-degree appraisal, Peer Review, Self-Review, Essay appraisal, Graphic rating scale, forced-choice rating, critical incident appraisal, Management-by-objectives approach, ranking methods (“11.2 Appraisal Methods – Human Resource Management,” n.d.). Considering the limitations and scope of the study, only first three types of performance appraisal are reviewed.

a) 360-degree

The 360-degree appraisal is the most exhaustive and exorbitant sort

of evaluations Milliman et al., 1994). It offers an elective technique by which associations can acquire helpful performance data about workers and make them more responsible to their different clients. Instead of having a solitary individual play judge, a 360-degree evaluation acts more like a jury. It incorporates self-evaluations, peer survey, and upward appraisals; input is looked for from everybody. It allows individuals to know how others see them, to see their abilities and style, and may enhance correspondences between individuals. The general population, who manage the worker every day, make a pool of data on which the administrator may act. This gives input from both inward and outside clients to get a more extensive, more exact point of view on representatives. The benefits of the 360 degrees are: it gives a more complete perspective of worker performance, it expands inclusion and believability of the performance evaluation, have a solid effect of conduct and performance, input from peers upgrades representative self-improvement. It extraordinarily expands correspondence and shared objectives and builds responsibility of workers to their clients. A portion of the inconveniences are: they are tedious and more officially mind boggling, broad giving and accepting input which can be scary to a few representatives, expensive and requires preparing and huge change push to work successfully (Milliman et al. 1994).

b) Self-Review

Self-Reviews depend on the possibility that representatives are most comfortable with their work, and that their contribution is basic. Representatives rate themselves on a few criteria, often with a formal study shape, and propose enhancements. They help to clear up their own objectives and uncover territories of shortcoming, so they might be taken a shot at. Meyer (1991) said that self-audit changes the part of the administrator to guide, instead of judge. With this part, the administrator can accomplish more to help individuals. He additionally brings up that self-survey improves the subordinate's poise and confidence. Including the worker as an equivalent in the audit procedure will probably build promise to activity designs, making

the whole procedure both additionally fulfilling and more gainful. Self-audits tend to have low corona blunder and result in little printed material for supervisors. Be that as it may, individuals may not see their own lacks as others do, so self-survey ought to be utilized close by different strategies.

c) Peer Review

Peer review might be outlined by three to six specialists, to set the objectives, advantages, and goals of the program, plan a criteria-based performance assessment framework and direct an experimental run program. Individuals ought to be urged to give input on the framework itself. Preparing and support ought to be accessible. Companion audits frequently have an abnormal state of labourer acknowledgment and contributions tend to be steady, assignment applicable, and precise. By helping associates to see each other's work, and via airing grievances in a non-debilitating way, peer surveys may likewise assist individuals with getting along better. Williams and Kleiners (1996) stated that "the employee has the opportunity to appeal his or her case to a panel of peers, whose decision is binding on the employee as well as the company". For the association, this implies higher performance. For the labourer, this implies a superior work environment and less dissatisfaction.

d) Attitude

A disposition can be characterized as a constructive or contrary assessment of individuals, objects, occasions, thoughts or pretty much anything in your condition (Zimbardo et al, 1999). All demeaners take a position either positive or negative, yet they can differ in force. As demonstrated by Robbins and Judge (2001), mindsets are evaluative decrees either perfect or negative about things, people, or events. They reflect how we feel about something. Social researchers use the term attitude to imply people's evaluation of in every way that really matters any piece of their social world (Olson and Maio, 2003; Petty, et al 2003). Individuals can have ideal or negative responses to issues, thoughts, protests, a conduct, or whole social

gatherings. A few Attitudes are very steady and impervious to change while others might be temperamental and demonstrate impressive changeability relying upon the circumstance (Schwarz and Bohner, 2001). We may hold a few states of mind with extraordinary sureness, while different mentalities might be generally misty or questionable.

States of mind can impact our contemplations, regardless of whether they are not reflected in our clear conduct. Also, while a significant number of our demeanors are unequivocal mentality cognizant and reportable different states of mind might be verifiable Attitudes wild and maybe not deliberately open to us (Fazio and Oslon, 2003).

3. Theoretical Framework

Based on the reviewed literature, the study uses the following theoretical framework, where proposed relationship of 360 degree appraisal, self-review, and peer review is positive with employees’ work attitude. The null hypothesis for the regression analysis is that “360 degree appraisal, self-review, and peer review have no significant effect on employees’ work attitude”.

4. Research Design

The current research is an explanatory study where the objective is to analyze the effect of different types of performance appraisal on employees’ work attitude. The study follows deductive approach where focus is on quantitative analysis. The study develops a questionnaire based on five points Likert scale. The reliability of the questionnaire is checked through Cronbach alpha test. For descriptive statistics, the study uses mean, median, mode, and standard deviation. Regression analysis was used for the testing of hypothesis.

4.1 Research population

Population refers to the group of people which forms the subject of the study in a survey. In this study, the population was the employees of International Organization (INGOs) management, senior staff and middle management staff. The criteria for sample selection was the general awareness of the 360-degree performance appraisal, Peer Review, and self-review performance appraisal. A total sample size of 150 was selected and response rate was 100%. The study uses purposive sampling where it best fits the criteria for sample selection. The selected respondents in total sample is categorized as follow in Table 1:

Table 1: Sample Size Categorization

Category	No. of Employees	Percentage (%)
Senior Management Staff	41	27%
Middle Management staff	73	49%
Lower Management staff	36	24%
Total	150	100

Source: Authors' Compilation

Reliability Table

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Standardized Items Cronbach Alpha	N of Items
360 Degree	.835	06
Self-Review	.922	06
Peer Review	.908	06
Work Attitude	.614	06

Source: Authors' Compilation

The table 2 shows the values for Cronbach's Alpha for all the four variables separately which analyzes the reliability of the data collection instrument. Values of alpha for all the variables are above .60 which confirms the reliability of the questionnaire.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Three Sixty Degree	150	1.00	3.50	2.0622	.62735
Peer Review	150	1.00	3.80	2.2173	.71717
Self Review	150	1.00	4.00	2.1067	.73839

Work Attitude	150	1.00	2.83	2.1378	.52447
Valid N (list wise)	150				

Source: Authors' Compilation

The table 3 shows some descriptive statistics for the given variables. Table shows a total of 150 observations. The minimum value is 1 in each variable case while mean value is around 2. The standard deviation for 360 degree, peer review, self-review, and work attitude are 0.62735, 0.71717, 0.73839, and 0.52447 respectively.

Correlation Analysis

Table 4: Correlations Coefficients

		360Degree	Peer Review	Self Review	Work Attitude
360Degree	Pearson Correlation	1	.644**	.922**	.815**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Peer Review	Pearson Correlation	.644**	1	.571**	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Self Review	Pearson Correlation	.922**	.571**	1	.748**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Work Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.815**	.679**	.748**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' Compilation

The table 4 shows the correlation among the variables. All the figures at diagonals are equal to 1 which is between the same variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient for work attitude against 360 degree appraisal, peer review, and self-review is .815, .679, and .748 respectively. The table shows that correlation of work attitude against all variables is significant and positive.

Model Summary Table

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.839 ^a	.704	.698	.28807

a. Predictors: (Constant), SelfReview, PeerReview, ThreeSixtyDegree

b. Dependent Variable: WorkAttitude

Source: Authors' Compilation

The Table 5 is the model outline consequence of the relapse appraisal for 360-degree performance appraisal, Self-Review and Peer Review Performance Appraisal and its impact on representative attitude towards work. The adjusted R square shows that 69.8% of the change in dependent variable is because of the independent variables used in the study. The rest of the 30.2% of the change in dependent variable is because of the factors which are not included in the research study.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 6: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	92.158	3	30.719	177.962	.000 ^a
	Residual	25.202	146	.173		
	Total	117.360	149			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-Review Performance Appraisal, Peer Review Performance Appraisal, 360-degree Performance Appraisal

b. Dependent Variable: Attitude towards work

Source: Authors' Compilation

The table 6 shows the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the mentioned variables. ANOVA test the significance of the model for which the null hypothesis is that model is not significant. The table shows that the value of significance is 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Based on significance value, we reject null hypothesis and consider the model used in the research paper is significant.

Coefficients Estimation and Hypothesis Testing

Table 7: Coefficients Estimation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	.136	.127		1.072	.285
	360-degree	-.547	.151	-.387	-3.634	.000
	Peer Review	1.347	.064	1.050	20.906	.000
	Self-Review	.116	.119	.096	.970	.334

Dependent Variable: Attitude towards work

Source: Authors' Compilation

5. Findings

The table shows the value of constant is .136 which shows that in absence of the performance appraisal types, still the work attitude of employees will be there by .136 units. For hypothesis testing, the study takes help from significance values. 360 degree appraisal has a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 confirming that 360-degree has a negative significant impact on employees' work attitude. Literature suggested positive effect of 360 degree appraisal on work attitude. Possible reason for a negative beta of 360 degree may be the lack of awareness about the 360 degree appraisal type. It is often used with negative connotations among employees and a tool for punishment in organization. The peer review also shows a significant impact on employees' work attitude but the impact is positive as proposed. Self-Review is insignificant with p-value more than 0.05 suggesting it has no role in changing employees' attitude towards work.

6. Conclusion

Performance appraisal goes with a lot of remuneration and package for both the specialist and the organization. In any case, it should not be ignored that performance assessment similarly has its shortcomings or negative effects towards the employees and the organizations. However, it appears that the beneficial outcomes exceed the negative impacts. Preference was the principle deficiency to performance evaluation. It was evident from the appraisal that performance evaluation should by large be grasped by all organizations, with the goal that great and viable outcomes prompting the acknowledgment of authoritative objectives can be accomplished.

The study uses data from international non-governmental organizations and selected a sample of 150 individuals based on purposive sam-

pling technique. The study analyzed the relationship between performance appraisal types and employees' work attitude. The study used correlation and regression analysis for achieving the mentioned objectives. The findings suggest that 360 degree negative effect the employees' attitude towards work while peer review has a positive impact on employees' attitude towards work. Self-review was found with no effect on employees' work attitude. Findings of the study can be used both by academicians and practitioners for a variety of purposes like policy making and implementation of such policies. In future, the scope of the research can be extended to other type of organizations as well with some advance analysis techniques.

7. Recommendation

In view of the findings of the study, the research study recommends that organizations in Afghanistan should focus on 360 degree and peer review appraisal because these methods of appraisals almost cover every aspect of the performance. The scope of the research analysis should be expanded to other types of organizations as well to increase the generalizability of the findings. Future researches can incorporate other types of performance appraisal to relate them with employees' work attitude.

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